

How to make a Portable Application

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Abstract

This article describe how to make any simple application Portable. The process described only works for standalone EXE which is converted in such a way that, it will appear in Portable Apps start menu.

Index Terms

PortableApps, Make, Portable, Windows, Applications, USB

I. PROCEDURE

Consider that the `TorBrowser`, which we will convert to `PortableApps`. It will then become available in the `PortableApps Start Menu`. Then create the following `directory` structure:

1. Open the `[root]` folder of the `PortableApps` application.
2. Then open the `[root]\PortableApps` folder and enter it.
3. Then create a folder name `[root]\PortableApps\. In our example, this folder is named [root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable.`
4. Then inside this folder create two folders named:
 - `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App`
 - `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\Data`
5. Then inside the `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App` folder, create the following two folders:
 - `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo`
 - `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\Browser` where `Browser` is the application directory containing the actual `TorBrowser` executable and its associated paths. It can be whatever you want based your application. But this folder is where your application main executable will be located.
6. Inside `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo` directory create a directory named `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo\Launcher`.
7. Inside the `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\Data` directory create a directory named `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\Data\settings`.

The overall directory structure is as follows for our example `TorBrowser` application:

- `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable`
- `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App`
- `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo`
- `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo\Launcher`
- `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\Browser` (directory containing the actual executable)
- `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\Data`
- `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\Data\settings`

Inside the `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\Data\settings` directory, create a blank text file named `TorBrowserPortableSettings.ini` which is the following naming format:

`<application name>PortableSettings.ini`.

Inside the folder `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\Browser` (directory containing the actual executable), copy the application executable and all related files.

Inside the folder `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo`, place the application icon file and name it `appicon.ico`.

Inside the folder `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo`, create a file named `appinfo.ini`. Then open this file in `Notepad`. Then do the following:

```
[Format]
Type=PortableApps.comFormat
Version=3.5

[Details]
Name=TorBrowser Portable
AppId=TorBrowserPortable
Publisher=Vista Software & PortableApps.com
Homepage=https://portableapps.com/apps/utilities/tinytask_portable
Category=Internet
Description=Tor Browser
Language=English

[License]
Shareable=true
OpenSource=false
Freeware=true
CommercialUse=true

[Version]
PackageVersion=1.77.0.0
DisplayVersion=1.77

[Control]
Icons=1
Start=TorBrowserPortable.exe
BaseAppID=%BASELAUNCHERPATH%\App\Browser\firefox.exe
```

The above file `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo\appinfo.ini` format is as following:

```
[Format]
Type=PortableApps.comFormat
Version=3.5

[Details]
Name=<Name of your Application, space can be included> Portable
AppId=<Portable Application root folder>Portable
Publisher=Vista Software & PortableApps.com
Homepage=https://portableapps.com/apps/utilities/tinytask_portable
Category=<Application Category from the list shown in figure for "Portable App Categories">
Description=<An english description of the program>
Language=English

[License]
Shareable=true
```

```

OpenSource=false
Freeware=true
CommercialUse=true

[Version]
PackageVersion=1.77.0.0
DisplayVersion=1.77

[Control]
Icons=1
Start=<Application Name>Portable.exe
BaseAppID=%BASELAUNCHERPATH%\App\<executable directory>\<actual executable name>
.exe

```


Fig. 1. Portable App Categories

Open the folder, `[root]\PortableApps\TorBrowserPortable\App\AppInfo\Launcher` and create a blank text file named `TorBrowserPortable.ini` which is of format `<Application Name>Portable.ini`. Then enter the following texts:

```

[Launch]
ProgramExecutable=Browser\firefox.exe

```

This file `<Application Name>Portable.ini` have the format:

```
[Launch]
ProgramExecutable=<actual executable directory>\<application executable>.exe
```

After complete the above processes, then launch the portable apps application and run the application named `PortableApps.com Launcher` listed under `Development` category.

The first screen will be as shown in Fig. 2. Click the `Next` button.

Fig. 2. First screen of portable apps

Then the next screen is shown in Fig. 3. There click on the `...` button and select the directory of our portable application `TorBrowserPortable`. Once the full-path of the folder is shown in the edit box aside. Then click on the `Go` button.

Fig. 3. Select the Portable Application Folder and click Go.

The process will complete and a launcher file named **<Application Name>Portable.exe** (eg. **TorBrowserPortable.exe**) will appear in the folder. Then on the next screen errors will be reported. In case no error will report, click **Finish** button on last screen Fig. 4 and exit the application.

Fig. 4.

After the application completes, and the launcher file is created, the application can be executed by double clicking the

launcher file. If the portable apps application is restarted, the application will be listed under the specified category as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. TorBrowser is now listed in Portable Apps start menu.